

Comprehensive investigation of matrix effect evaluation approaches for reliable quantification in bioanalysis using UHPLC-MS/MS

Hana Kočová Vlčková , Kateřina Plachká , František Švec , Lucie Nováková*

Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Králové, Charles University, Heyrovského 1203, Hradec Králové, 500 03, Czech Republic

HIGHLIGHTS

- Two matrix effect evaluation approaches were compared: post-extraction addition and slope-based evaluation.
- Appropriate calibration model selection is essential for reliable matrix effect evaluation.
- Different matrix effects were observed depending on the selected weighting or transformation model.
- The slope-based approach underestimated matrix effects because translational effects were not included.
- A new calculation for translational matrix effect based on calibration curve intercepts was proposed.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Xiu-Ping Yan

Keywords:

Matrix effect
Mass spectrometry
Post-extraction addition
Calibration curve slope
Calibration model

ABSTRACT

Background: Matrix effect (ME) evaluation is an indispensable part of the method development and validation when using ultra-high performance liquid chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS). The rotational and translational matrix effects are often observed. The rotational matrix effect depends on the analyte concentration and affects the slope of the calibration function, while the translational matrix effect is independent of the analyte concentration and affects the intercept of the calibration function. Two matrix effect evaluation strategies, the post-extraction addition and the comparison of calibration curve slopes, are the most widely used for the quantitative ME evaluation. The post-extraction addition approach recommended by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) guideline is considered the reference approach. However, the extent to which these approaches provide comparable results has not been systematically assessed.

Results: We evaluated the suitability of the calibration curve slope approach for quantifying ME. Two ME evaluation strategies were systematically compared using ESI-UHPLC-MS/MS in both negative and positive ionization modes for the analysis of 26 compounds in serum. Various calibration models, including $1/X^0$, $1/X$, and $1/X^2$ weighting or logarithmic transformation, were assessed. None of the tested models provided over-estimated results compared to the post-extraction addition approach. However, several models exhibited

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: nol@email.cz (L. Nováková).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2026.345642>

Received 9 March 2026; Received in revised form 6 May 2026; Accepted 7 May 2026

Available online 9 May 2026

0003-2670/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

underestimated results. Thus, we developed a new approach for calculation of ME taking into account also the translational ME expressed by the intercept of the calibration curve. The accuracy of the new approach was subsequently determined using three different matrices and two different instrumental platforms.

Significance: It is not advisable to rely solely on the calibration curve slope approach for accurate estimation of ME unless translational ME derived from calibration curve intercept are also involved in calculation. Therefore, a novel intercept-based equation was proposed for the calculation of translational matrix effects. The total matrix effect, obtained as the sum of the slope- and intercept-derived contributions, closely corresponds to matrix effects determined by the post-extraction addition approach.

1. Introduction

Ultra-high performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (UHPLC-MS) offers numerous advantages, such as rapid analyses, high selectivity, and high sensitivity, enabling the reliable determination of analytes in complex matrices [1]. However, even with the advanced instrumentation, matrix effects remain a major analytical challenge. In particular, matrix effect can significantly affect mass spectrometry (MS) response and therefore must be carefully evaluated during method development and validation [2].

The effect caused by components of the sample other than the target analyte is referred to as matrix effect (ME) according to IUPAC [3,4], representing the combined effect of all components from the sample. On the other hand, the term interference describes the effect of the specified/identified component on the measurement [4–6]. Several types of ME can be distinguished. Translational matrix effect or baseline interference is usually independent of analyte concentration and affects the intercept of a calibration curve [7]. It is also called the background effect, as it occurs even in the absence of the target analyte [3], and can be interpreted as a systematic shift in the analytical response independent of analyte concentration, typically associated with background signals, droplet physiochemistry changes, or baseline contributions introduced by the sample matrix. In contrast, rotational matrix effect or proportional interference is generally proportional to the analyte signal and thus affects the slope of the calibration curve [7]. Absolute ME describes the effect of the matrix in a given sample [8], whereas relative ME describes the variation in ME between different sources of samples [8].

In mass spectrometry, the term matrix effect has a narrower definition, referring specifically to changes in ionization efficiency and resulting deviation in analytical response [8–10]. The ME typically manifests as a signal enhancement or suppression [11,12], thereby severely compromising key parameters of quantitative analysis, including linearity, accuracy, precision, and sensitivity. This effect arises primarily from altered ionization efficiency caused by co-eluting components such as endogenous and exogenous compounds, buffer constituents, and potential impurities [13].

Several factors have been hypothesized to cause the signal suppression widely reported in LC-MS [14,15]. The main ones include the competition between the analyte and co-eluting compounds for the available charge and access to the droplet surface, changes in liquid phase viscosity affecting spray formation and evaporation, formation of solid particles and/or analyte binding, the ion-pairing reactions between analytes/co-eluting compounds, and neutralization of analytes. These factors contribute to analyte-dependent behavior [3,16–19]. The type of ionization source can also significantly affect the extent of ME suppression and/or enhancement [3,16–19]. To date, only one hypothesis has been proposed to explain ME enhancement, suggesting that matrix components may act as dopants, i.e., as additives that enhance ionization efficiency thereby increasing the analyte signal [20].

The ME can be compensated, minimized, and/or eliminated. The compensation approaches include the use of stable isotopically labeled internal standard (SIL-IS) and external calibration using matrix-matched

samples. ME can be minimized by sample dilution, appropriate sample preparation methods that effectively remove matrix components, modification of ionization conditions and/or change of ion source type, and re-optimization of the separation method to avoid the co-elution of matrix compounds [2,16,21]. Unfortunately, it is often impossible to completely eliminate the ME from LC-MS analyses; therefore, their compensation is required.

Several strategies have been proposed for the ME evaluation. First, post-column infusion is suggested for qualitative ME evaluation. Ionization suppression or enhancement can be observed as positive or negative MS signal changes from the chromatographic baseline [14,16]. Second, the post-extraction addition approach described by Matuszewski et al. [8] allows the quantification of matrix effects. This method compares the peak area of the standard dissolved in a selected dilution solvent (A) with the peak area of a blank matrix sample extracted by an optimized procedure and subsequently spiked with the analytes at the same concentration as the standard sample (B). The equation is $ME = B/A * 100$ (Eq. (1)). A value of less than 100% indicates ion suppression, while a value exceeding 100% indicates ion enhancement [8,14,17]. Chambers et al. further modified the Matuszewski equation [22], allowing ME to be expressed as a percentage enhancement (a value > 0%) and/or suppression (a value < 0%) of the MS signal using the equation $ME = (B/A - 1) * 100$ (Eq. (2)). Finally, a simple comparison of the slopes of standard and matrix calibration curves [23], here referred to as the slope-based approach, can be also used to quantify the ME according to the equation $ME = \Delta S/S_{STD} * 100$ (Eq. (3)), where ΔS is the difference between the slopes of the standard (S_{STD}) and matrix calibration curves (S_M). This requires the selection of a regression model that fits the experimental data. Least square linear regression is commonly used to fit experimental chromatographic data to a linear calibration curve [24–26]. Here, the same emphasis is given to the different data points across the calibration curve. Since the absolute variation is more significant at higher concentrations, the higher points dominate the linear regression model. There are several ways to reduce this effect. Plotting the x-axis on a logarithmic scale instead of a linear scale allows the data points to be spread over the entire range. Another way is to weigh the data inversely with the concentration. These transformations should also reduce the overall method error and improve the quality of the analytical results [24]. Thus, they also affect the evaluation of matrix effects.

ME evaluation is an integral part of LC-MS analyses of complex samples. However, various method validation guidelines propose different procedures for ME assessment depending on the availability of blank matrix and the sample preparation strategy [27–30]. Currently, the post-extraction addition method is the method of choice in regulated bioanalytical laboratories, as it is defined in several guidelines, such as the EMA guideline [27]. Nevertheless, a number of guidelines still require the evaluation of calibration curve slopes as a necessary step in ME evaluation [3]. However, the extent to which these approaches provide comparable quantitative results has not been systematically assessed.

The main objective of this study was to systematically evaluate two

quantitative approaches for matrix effect evaluation, i.e., the post-extraction addition and slope-based approach, using serum as a complex matrix and a non-selective protein precipitation procedure. Based on the observed limitations of slope-based evaluation, a novel intercept-based equation for the calculation of translational matrix effects was introduced. By combining translational matrix effects derived from calibration curve intercepts with rotational matrix effects derived from calibration curve slopes, the new approach provides a more reliable and comprehensive framework for ME evaluation. The accuracy and applicability of the new approach were subsequently demonstrated using a validation set of compounds analyzed in three different matrices on two various UHPLC–MS/MS platforms.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals and reagents

Evaluation set of analytes: reference standards of atenolol (ATE), atorvastatin (ATO), dexamethasone (DEX), estrone (EST), hydrocortisone (HYD), (s)-(+)-ibuprofen (IBU), caffeine (COF), paracetamol (PAR), pefloxacin (PEF), rutin (RUT), tamsulosin (TAM), telmisartan (TEL), tetracycline (TTC), tryptophan (TRY), uracil (URA), and vardenafil (VAR) were provided by Sigma-Aldrich (Germany). Reference standards of acebutolol (ACE), daclatasvir (DAC), ritonavir (RIT), and sofosbuvir (SOF) were purchased from Medchemexpress (Germany). Reference standards of maraviroc (MAR), pitavastatin (PIT), and pravastatin (PRA) were obtained from Toronto Research Chemicals (Canada). Reference standard of indomethacin (IND) was provided by Thermo Fisher Scientific (USA), atomoxetine (AMO) by Zentiva (Czech Republic), and salicylic acid (SAL) by Fluka (France).

Validation set of analytes: Reference standards of progesterone, 17 α -hydroxyprogesterone, 5 α -dihydroxyprogesterone, 5 α -pregnane-3 β -ol-20-on, cortisol, 11-deoxycortisol, 5 α -dihydrotestosterone, and androsterone were purchased from Steraloids Inc. (Newport, RI, USA). Reference standards of dexamethasone and testosterone were provided by Serva Electrophoresis GmbH (Heidelberg, Germany). Reference standards of hydroxyphenylpropionic acid, ethylparaben, propylparaben, acebutolol, pindolol, dopamine, serotonin, hydroxyindole-3-acetic acid, and cinnamic acid were purchased by Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany). Reference standards of simvastatin, atorvastatin, lovastatin, pitavastatin, fluvastatin lactone, and atorvastatin lactone were provided from Toronto Research Chemicals (Ontario, Canada). Reference standards of ritonavir and lopinavir were obtained from Target-Mol (Boston, MA, USA). Reference standards of simeprevir, reserpine, zidovudine, rutin, quercetin, isorhamnetin, 4-methylcatechol were provided from Medchemexpress (Germany).

Methanol (MeOH), acetonitrile (ACN), water, and formic acid (purity >99%), all of them LC-MS grade, were provided by Sigma Aldrich (Czech Republic).

Lyophilized human serum LYO HUM N was purchased from Erba Lachema (Czech Republic). Fresh apple juice was purchased from common supermarket named Albert (Czech Republic).

Biological samples of urine were collected from the volunteers from the Department of Analytical Chemistry, Faculty of Pharmacy in Hradec Kralove, Charles University. 5 men and women aged 30–45 provided their urine. All volunteers provided written informed consent with the use of the urine for scientific purposes. The urine was collected immediately prior to the analysis. A pooled rat plasma sample was prepared from six plasma samples obtained from male normotensive Wistar rats (Charles River, Düsseldorf, Germany). It was provided by the Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, Faculty of Pharmacy, Charles University. The plasma samples were stored at -80°C until analysis.

2.2. Ultra-high performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry

All evaluation experiments were carried out on an Acquity Ultra Performance LC (UPLC) system (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) coupled to a Micromass Quattro Micro API benchtop triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (Waters, Milford, MA, USA). A volume of 5 μL was injected on an Acquity BEH C18 analytical column (100 mm \times 2.1 mm; 1.7 μm). The analytes were separated under gradient elution with 0.1% formic acid in water (eluent A) and ACN (eluent B) at a flow rate of 0.3 mL min^{-1} . The gradient started with 5% of eluent B and increased to 98% over 8.5 min. The isocratic step at 98% eluent B was then kept for 1.5 min at the end of the gradient. At 10.1 min, the percentage of eluent B was returned to the original conditions of 5%. The total chromatographic analysis time, including column equilibration, was 12 min. The triple quadrupole was operated in electrospray (ESI) mode individually in positive and negative polarity. The conditions were set up as follows: capillary voltage 0.75 kV in ESI positive and -2.5 kV in ESI negative, RF lens voltage 0.5 V; extractor voltage 3.0 V; source temperature 130 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The desolvation gas (nitrogen) flow was set at 800 L hr^{-1} and at a temperature of 450 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Nitrogen was also used as a cone gas with a flow rate of 120 L h^{-1} . Argon was used as a collision gas. Selected reaction monitoring (SRM) transitions were optimized for each analyte in ESI positive and ESI negative to select appropriate precursor ion, fragment ion, cone voltage, and collision energy. The final SRM transition settings are listed in Supplementary Material (SM) Table S1. The MassLynx 4.1 software was used for data acquisition, and TargetLynx software for peak integration and data processing.

Validation experiments of new approach were measured on two UHPLC-MS/MS systems, ACQUITY UPLC I-Class system (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) coupled with Xevo-TQ-XS triple quadrupole (Waters, Milford, MA, USA) and Agilent 1290 Infinity II UHPLC system coupled with an Agilent 6495 Triple Quadrupole MS system (Agilent Technologies, Santa Clara, USA). The validation set of analytes was separated on an Acquity BEH C18 analytical column (100 mm \times 2.1 mm, 1.7 μm) following the injection of 2.5 μL of the sample. Gradient elution using 0.1% formic acid (A) and acetonitrile (B) at flow rate 0.35 mL/min were used in this program: 0–5 min, 2–98% ACN followed by 2 min column equilibration at 2% ACN. The column temperature was maintained at 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the autosampler temperature was set at 8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The Xevo-TQ-XS system was operated with ESI source in separate experiments in positive and negative ion modes under the following conditions: capillary voltage 2.0/ -1.0 kV (ESI positive/ESI negative), ion source temperature 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, desolvation temperature 500 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, cone gas (nitrogen) flow 300 L/h, desolvation gas (nitrogen) flow 1200 L/h, nebulizer gas (nitrogen) pressure 7.0 bar. The Agilent 6495 Triple Quadrupole system with ESI source in the positive mode was set up: capillary voltage 4.5 kV, nozzle voltage 2.0 kV, drying gas temperature 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and flow 12 L/min, sheath gas (nitrogen) temperature 250 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and flow 6 L/min, nebulizer 30 psi, and high/low pressure RF iFunnel parameter 135 V/80 V. SRM transitions were optimized for each analyte and both MS/MS systems. SRM transitions and their settings for both systems are listed in SM Table S2 and S3.

2.3. Preparation of standard solutions and spiked matrix

2.3.1. Preparation of evaluation set of standard solutions and spiked serum

All analytes included in evaluation set together with their abbreviation are listed in SM Table S4. Their standard substances were dissolved in suitable solvent at a concentration of 0.5–1 mg mL^{-1} (SM Table S4). All stock standard solutions were freshly prepared every two weeks and stored at 8 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The compounds were divided into three mixtures

according to their retention times to eliminate the co-elution and obtain an adequate number of acquisition points per peak with respect to the dwell time of the used MS system. These three stock mixtures of compounds at a concentration of $10 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ were prepared by dilution in 5% ACN in water. All the mixed solutions were further diluted with 5% ACN in water to obtain the required concentration levels within the calibration range.

Lyophilized serum was prepared according to the manufacturer's recommendations in 5 mL water and used as the matrix. Serum was immediately processed by protein precipitation (Section 2.4) followed by spiking with appropriate concentrations of standard mixtures. These standard and sample solutions (i.e., spiked serum) were prepared in the concentration range of 2 ng mL^{-1} – 512 ng mL^{-1} to examine the calibration curve, range, and matrix effects. The tested concentration levels were 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256, and 512 ng mL^{-1} .

2.3.2. Preparation of validation set of standard solutions and spiked matrix

The analytes included in validation set are listed in SM Table S5. Their standard substances were dissolved in suitable solvent at a concentration of 0.3 - 1 mg mL^{-1} (SM Table S5). The appropriate solvent was selected according to the different solubilities of compounds. The mixed solutions of tested analytes were prepared by the same way as for evaluation set of standard solutions.

The matrices were processed using appropriate sample preparation methods: plasma samples were subjected to protein precipitation, whereas urine and juice samples were prepared by dilution, see in Section 2.4. Subsequently, all samples were spiked with appropriate concentrations of standard mixtures. These standard and sample solutions (i.e., spiked matrix) were prepared in the concentration range of 0.01 ng mL^{-1} – 100 ng mL^{-1} to examine the calibration curve and matrix effects. The tested concentration levels were 0.01, 0.025, 0.05, 0.1, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 2.5, 5, 10, 25, 50, 100 ng mL^{-1} . Different concentration levels compared to the evaluation experiments were selected owing to differences in instrumental sensitivity.

2.4. Sample preparation

Protein precipitation was used as the sample preparation method for plasma and lyophilized serum. A volume of $400 \mu\text{L}$ ACN was added into $200 \mu\text{L}$ blank lyophilized serum or rat plasma. The mixture was incubated for 10 min at room temperature and centrifuged at $21\,255 \text{ g}$, 20°C for 10 min. The collected supernatant was evaporated to dryness under vacuum and reconstituted in dilution solvent, i.e., 5% ACN in water.

Urine and juice matrices were ten times diluted by 5% ACN in water after the previous filtration through the PTFE syringe filter ($0.22 \mu\text{m}$).

2.5. Calibration curve, calibration range, and matrix effects

Standard and matrix solutions (i.e., spiked serum) were used to evaluate the standard and matrix calibration curves, calibration range, and matrix effects. Each standard solution was serially diluted in the concentration range specified in Section 2.3. The individual matrix solutions were prepared from the blank matrix treated with protein precipitation. The resulting supernatants were then spiked with the minimum amount of reference standards mixture (<5 % of the total volume prepared, i.e., $10 \mu\text{L}$) to avoid excessive dilution of the biological material and misinterpretation of the results. The analytes were added after extraction, as the focus of the study was to evaluate matrix effects using well-established post-extraction approach. The analyte concentrations in matrix calibration solutions were identical to those in the standard calibration solutions.

For the purpose of this study, linear regression models had to be selected because of the need to define a single calibration curve slope to calculate matrix effects. Other regression functions typically provide a regression equation with multiple slopes. The least squares regression without weighting ($1/X^0$), with logarithmic (Ln) transformation, and with $1/X$ and $1/X^2$ weighting schemes were evaluated.

The evaluated regression analysis parameters included % error at individual concentrations, the coefficient of determination, and the slope and intercept with their corresponding p-values. The % error of each calibration point was acceptable within $\pm 20\%$ of the nominal concentration at the LLOQ and within $\pm 15\%$ at all other concentration levels. The $\% \sum$ -error parameter was calculated as the sum of all unacceptable absolute values of % errors. If all % errors in the calibration range were acceptable according to EMA guidelines, the worst % error was considered the $\% \sum$ -error parameter. While the limits for % error are precisely defined in the bioanalytical guidelines (EMA), no universal threshold is established for r^2 . In the context of bioanalysis, 95% confidence is the most defined, i.e., a coefficient of determination of 0.95. High confidence values are advantageous for reliable quantification.

Two calibration ranges were defined for the purpose of this study: the entire calibration range from the lowest concentration to the highest concentration of 512 ng mL^{-1} and the narrowed calibration range from the lower limit of quantification (LLOQ) to the upper limit of quantification (ULOQ). First, the entire calibration range was defined. This range was the same for all models but differed for each compound. The lowest concentrations were determined as the concentrations with a signal-to-noise ratio ≥ 10 for each compound individually. This range was used to compare tested models in terms of % error and coefficient of determination. Secondly, the narrowed calibration range was defined for each compound and each model. This range was created by excluding the upper or lower calibration points when necessary to meet the % error requirement for all concentration points. The narrowed calibration range was determined only for analytes meeting the criteria of at least 6 concentration levels. The narrowed calibration ranges were then compared with respect to the type of used calibration model and then used to calculate the ME using the slope-based approach.

Matrix effects were evaluated using two main quantitative approaches: the slope-based approach and the post-extraction addition method described by Matuszewski et al. [8]. The same data, i.e. the same samples, the same concentration levels, and a single measurement, were used to ensure a meaningful comparison. According to the EMA guideline, matrix effect evaluation using the post-extraction addition approach requires that the matrix is first subjected to the appropriate sample preparation procedure and subsequently spiked with analytes. For this reason, the same workflow was consistently applied also for the slope-based approach. Equations for ME calculation using both approaches are shown in Introduction (Eq. (2) and Eq. (3)). Several categories were created to describe the obtained ME. An ideal method showed ME 0%. Acceptable performance corresponded to ME within $\pm 20\%$, whereas ME higher than 20% was considered unacceptable.

In the last step, both evaluation approaches were compared. The statistical significance of the intercept was determined by statistical regression analysis, and intercepts with a p-value < 0.05 were considered significant. Subsequently, the comparison of intercepts between the matrix and standard calibration curve was carried out only for compounds where the intercept from the matrix calibration model was significant. This approach is referred to as the intercept-based approach. For this calculation, we propose the use of the equation $\text{ME}_I = \Delta I / R_{\text{LLOQ}} * 100$ (Eq. (4)), where the ΔI is the difference between the intercepts from the standard and matrix calibration curves corresponding to the difference in responses and the R_{LLOQ} is the analyte response at the

LLOQ levels of the standard calibration curve. The final value of ME is then equal to the sum of ME calculated by the slope- and intercept-based approaches $\sum ME = ME_S + ME_I$ (Eq. (5)). Thus, the comparison of the standard and matrix calibration curve could take into account both types of ME: rotational, i.e., comparison of slopes, and translational, i.e., comparison of intercepts.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Matrix effect evaluation using calibration curve slopes

3.1.1. The selection of calibration models

Various weighting schemes such as $1/X^0$ (no weighting), $1/X$, and $1/X^2$ and logarithmic transformation (Ln) were tested and compared to evaluate their suitability. Firstly, all tested calibration models were compared across the entire calibration range using r^2 and % error (\sum -error). The wide calibration range very often used in the field of bioanalysis was defined as 2 – 512 ng/mL. The regular distribution of concentration levels such as 5, 10, 15, 20, etc. could not be used across this range due to the very high number of concentration levels required, in this case up to 100 points. A choice of larger concentration differences

would lead to inadequate coverage of low concentration levels. In addition, due to the testing of different calibration models, it was not possible to select univariate concentration levels that would be regularly distributed for all models. The concentration levels were selected based on a regular distribution for the logarithmic transformation of the data, which, according to the preliminary findings, showed the best overall behavior. Subsequently, calibration models were compared with narrowed calibration ranges defined according to the % error limits for each compound and calibration model (Section 2.5).

The calibration models were studied for 20 compounds in positive mode and 11 compounds in negative ionization mode. The limited number of compounds in ESI negative was caused by the lower sensitivity, resulting in a very narrow calibration range with fewer calibration points (<6) than required by the EMA guideline for bioanalytical methods. Although it is possible to add calibration points within this range, such a narrow calibration range is not practical. In ESI positive, it was not possible to determine the calibration curve for only two compounds, uracil, and vardenafil, for the same reason.

The effect of each calibration model on % error differed, as illustrated in Figs. 1 and 2, with Fig. 1 summarizing overall \sum -errors across the calibration range and Fig. 2 depicting the distribution of

Fig. 1. Comparison of \sum -errors (ERROR, upper blue column) and coefficients of determination (r^2 , bottom yellow column) for individual calibration models (A) in ESI positive and (B) in ESI negative. The number in each bar corresponds to the number of compounds in the defined range. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. The violin plots showing distributions of % error at all tested concentration levels using density curves for tested compounds and calibration models ($1/X^0$ no weighting: blue, $1/X$ weighting: red, $1/X^2$ weighting: yellow and Ln transformation: dark gray) (A) in ESI positive and (B) in ESI negative. The colored asterisks mark the \sum -errors for tested compounds and calibration models, such as for violin graphs. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

individual % errors across concentration levels. Across the entire calibration range in both ionization modes, $1/X^0$ consistently exhibited the highest $\% \sum$ -errors and greatest variability of individual % errors. Moreover, no compound exhibited better results for the $1/X^0$ model than did the other models. In contrast, the $1/X^2$ and Ln model generally provided the lowest $\% \sum$ -errors and together with more balanced error distributions across the calibration range. For two compounds, acceptable $\% \sum$ -errors across the entire calibration range were achieved only using a non-linear model.

With respect to the coefficient of determination r^2 , values in ESI positive exceeded 0.9500 for 19 or 20 compounds depending on the selected model (Fig. 1A), with only tryptophan falling below this threshold for $1/X^2$ and Ln models. In ESI negative, r^2 values were generally higher than in ESI positive, likely reflecting lower MS responses, higher LLOQs, and a consequently narrower calibration range. Except for isolated cases (e.g., rutin with r^2 0.9406 for $1/X^2$), all models in ESI negative achieved $r^2 > 0.9500$ (Fig. 1B). No weighting model ($1/X^0$) frequently yielded very high r^2 values (>0.99) despite excessive % errors at low concentrations, indicating dominance of high response data points. On the other hand, $1/X^2$ weighting improved % errors at lower concentration levels but slightly reduced r^2 . Although a non-linear regression improved curve fitting across wide concentration ranges, a linear regression was required for slope-based ME evaluation. A logarithmic transformation proved the most appropriate for wide concentration ranges as it spreads the significance of individual concentration points over the entire concentration range, providing the lowest % error and high r^2 values.

Calibration models were further evaluated with respect to the width of the calibration range by % error acceptance criteria. Typically, exclusion of one or more low concentration points was necessary to comply with these criteria. The new narrowed calibration ranges were defined for each model and compound. The degree of narrowing differed between each calibration models (Fig. S1). In some cases, narrowing of the calibration range was so extensive that a calibration curves could not be constructed ("non-evaluated" in Fig. S1).

The Ln model retained the widest usable calibration range, whereas the $1/X^0$ model required the greatest narrowing. In ESI negative, narrowing the entire calibration range was required for more than half of compounds using the $1/X^0$ model but only rarely for the $1/X$ and $1/X^2$ models, and Ln model. However, in ESI positive, a substantially more pronounced narrowing of the entire calibration range was necessary, resulting in LLOQ increases of up to eight-fold for all calibration models. Consequently, $1/X^0$ model was excluded for several compounds due to impractical narrow ranges. All suitable models and their LLOQ changes are shown in Fig. S1.

3.1.2. Evaluation of matrix effects by comparison of calibration curve slopes

Matrix effects calculated by comparing calibration curve slopes were evaluated for all optimized calibration models defined for each compound within the narrowed calibration ranges according to the $\% \sum$ -error criteria (SM Table S6). SM Fig. S2 shows the detailed ME results where the colored points represent ME calculated by the slope-based approach.

In ESI positive, most compounds exhibited ME $< 20\%$ across all suitable calibration modes. The $1/X^0$ model could be applied only to limited number of compounds ($n=7$), yet all of them showed ME $< 20\%$. Similar ME results ($SD < 4$) for the $1/X$, $1/X^2$, and Ln models were obtained for all compounds with the ME $< 20\%$. Conversely, compounds with ME $> 20\%$ ($n=7$) showed a stronger dependence on the selected calibration model. The Ln model generally resulted in

substantially lower ME, approximately 5 to 50 times lower than the $1/X$ and $1/X^2$ models. An exception was observed for caffeine and hydrocortisone, for which the Ln model produced markedly higher ME values. These discrepancies were associated with pronounced rotational matrix effects, manifested as increasing matrix influence with decreasing analyte concentrations, reduced linear curve fitting, and higher % error in the matrix calibration curves. Since the logarithmic transformation distributes the weight of the concentration points across the entire calibration range, the strong rotational matrix effects in these cases were most apparent on the slopes, and considerable non-linear dependences were visually evident for the matrix calibration curves.

In ESI negative, the ME calculated from the slopes were $< 20\%$ for all compounds and calibration models, except for one compound in the Ln model. Only three compounds had ME $> 20\%$ and model dependent differences were therefore limited on this subset.

Overall, the selection of calibration model affected ME estimation, particularly for compounds exhibiting ME $> 20\%$.

3.2. Matrix effects calculated at the individual concentration levels

Matrix effects were calculated at each concentration level across the calibration range for all compounds and the results are shown in Fig. 3.

In ESI positive, ten compounds exhibited ME $< 20\%$ across the entire concentration range. For three compounds, ME beyond $\pm 20\%$ were confined to the lowest concentration levels. In contrast, the other analytes ($n=8$) exhibited markedly elevated ME across several concentration levels, reflecting stronger concentration dependent matrix influence.

These concentration dependencies, corresponding to rotational matrix effects, were characterized by a progressive increase in ME with decreasing analyte concentration. The magnitude of this effect varied between compounds, ranging from moderate deviations to pronounced enhancement or suppression at low concentration levels (Fig. 3). Only uracil (ME 81.5–86%) and atenolol (ME 30–45%) exhibited concentration independent ME throughout the calibration range.

As expected, overall ME values were substantially lower in ESI negative compared to ESI positive. This trend is consistent with differences in ionization mechanisms between positive and negative electrospray, where competition for protonation and charge availability in ESI positive typically increases susceptibility to suppression or enhancement effects [31]. Indeed, some compounds had ME in the hundreds to thousands of percent across the entire calibration range in ESI positive. In ESI negative, ME rarely exceeded 160% and predominantly occurred at the lowest concentration levels, whereas at higher concentrations ME generally remained below 40%. Although rotational matrix effects were observed for all analytes in negative mode, their magnitude was considerably reduced relative to ESI positive (Fig. 3).

3.3. Comparison of the two approaches for determination of matrix effects

An evaluation was carried out to determine whether both approaches provided comparable results and which calibration model within the slope-based approach yielded the most reliable results for matrix effect assessment during analytical method development and validation. The ME results of both approaches are compared in Fig. 4 and SM Fig. S2A. Fig. 4 shows the ME as acceptable/non-acceptable, i.e., below/above the set limit of 20%, and Fig. S2A shows the corresponding ME values for both approaches. The ME obtained by the post-extraction approach were considered as the reference values.

In ESI positive, ten compounds showed ME $< 20\%$ using both ME

Fig. 3. Matrix effects calculated at individual concentration levels (A) in ESI positive and (B) in ESI negative. Compound names highlighted in blue colour indicate analytes that did not meet the EMA calibration acceptance criteria, requiring a minimum of six calibration levels for regression analysis, and were therefore not evaluated for matrix effects using the slope-based approach. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

		POSITIVE MODE				NEGATIVE MODE			
		1/X ⁰	1/X	1/X ²	Ln	1/X ⁰	1/X	1/X ²	Ln
uracil	S								
	P	Red	Red	Red	Red				
paracetamol	S	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue				
	P	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue				
acebutolol	S			Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	P			Blue	Blue	Red	Red	Red	Red
maravirok	S				Blue				
	P				Red				
salicylic acid	S					Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	P					Red	Red	Red	Red
pravastatin	S					Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	P					Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
sofosbuvir	S	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	P	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Red	Red	Red
ritonavir	S		Blue	Blue	Blue				
	P	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue				
ibuprophen	S								
	P					Red	Red	Red	Red
estrone	S	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue				
	P	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue				
atenolol	S		Red	Red	Blue				
	P		Red	Red	Red				
caffeine	S	Blue	Blue	Blue	Red				
	P	Red	Red	Red	Red				
tetracycline	S		Blue	Red	Blue				
	P		Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
daclatasvir	S					Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	P		Blue	Blue	Blue	Red	Red	Red	Red
tamsulosin	S		Blue	Blue	Blue				
	P		Blue	Blue	Blue	Red	Red	Red	Red
atomoxetine	S		Blue	Blue	Blue				
	P		Blue	Blue	Blue				
telmisartan	S		Red	Red	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	P		Red	Red	Red	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
indomethacine	S	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue				
	P	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Red	Red	Red	Red
tryptophan	S		Blue	Blue					
	P		Red	Red					
perfloracin	S	Blue	Blue	Red	Blue				
	P	Red	Red	Red	Red				
rutin	S					Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	P					Red	Red	Red	Red
vardenafil	S					Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	P					Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
hydrocortisone	S		Blue	Blue	Red	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	P		Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
pitavastatin	S		Blue	Blue	Blue	Red	Red	Red	Red
	P		Blue	Red	Blue	Red	Red	Red	Red
dexamethasone	S		Blue	Blue	Blue				
	P		Blue	Blue	Blue				
atorvastatin	S	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue
	P	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue	Blue

Fig. 4. The heat plot comparing the matrix effect results obtained by the post-extraction (P) and slope-based (S) approaches using different calibration models (1/X⁰, 1/X, 1/X², and Ln). Blue - ME < 20%, red - ME > 20%, and darker color corresponds to increasing ME. White indicates that matrix effects were not evaluated. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

evaluation approaches and all suitable calibration models. This suggests that the slope-based approach provided results comparable to the post-extraction method without overestimating ME when values were below 20% (Fig. 4). However, SM Fig. 1A shows clear differences between the calibration models when ME exceeded 20%, particularly for the Ln model. The ME values obtained from the slopes of the Ln model differed substantially from those obtained with the other models and from the post-extraction approach. These differences were mainly observed for compounds with ME higher than 20% across most concentration levels and/or with ME outliers at low concentration levels. In these cases, the Ln model substantially underestimated ME compared with the reference ME calculated using the post-extraction approach.

The same trends are also visible in the second plot in SM Fig. S2A, which includes compounds with ME > 20%. Here, the Ln model did not agree with the ME of the post-extraction approach, and the accuracy of ME estimation increased in the order of $1/X^0$, $1/X$, and $1/X^2$ models. The $1/X^2$ model agreed best with the post-extraction ME at defined concentration levels (SM Fig. S2A). Nevertheless, the results from the $1/X^2$ model showed lower ME than the calculated reference ME. Overall, the ME from the $1/X^2$ model corresponded to the post-extraction ME at high concentration levels. A special situation occurred for hydrocortisone, caffeine, and tryptophan, as shown in SM Fig. S2A. These compounds exhibited pronounced translational matrix effects. Thus, none of the calibration curve slope ME adequately reflected the magnitude of ME determined at all concentration levels by post-extraction addition. The disagreement was most evident for Ln model, but substantial underestimation of ME was observed across all calibration models. These findings confirm the impact of strong concentration dependence and non-linear dependence on the matrix calibration.

In ESI negative, only some of the conclusions observed in ESI positive could be confirmed due to the significantly lower ME compared to ESI positive. The slope-based approach for ME assessment did not produce any overestimated values, i.e., higher ME results compared to the reference approach. However, it often produced underestimated results, i.e., lower ME results were often shown (Fig. 4 and SM Fig. S2B). The ME > 20% obtained by the post-extraction addition approach were confirmed by the slope-based approach only for one compound (hydrocortisone). The ME results in ESI negative were not dependent on the selected calibration model except for hydrocortisone, which exhibited worse ME results for the logarithmic model due to rotational ME as shown in SM Fig. S2B.

3.4. New matrix effect evaluation approach based on the calibration curve slope and intercept

The comparison of calibration curve slopes only takes into account rotational matrix effects. Thus, comparing slopes is not sufficient in cases where significant translational ME is observed. Therefore, the next step was to compare the intercepts of the standard and matrix calibration curves.

First, the statistical significance of the intercept was determined using the regression analysis. Intercepts with a p-value < 0.05 were marked as significant. The comparison of intercepts for matrix and standard calibration curves was subsequently carried out only for compounds and models exhibiting statistically significant intercepts in the matrix calibration curve. For this comparison and subsequent calculation of total ME, we proposed the use of the equations (Eq. (4) and Eq. (5)) illustrated in Fig. 5.

The difference between the intercepts (ΔI) from the standard and matrix models corresponds to the difference in responses. The effect of the translational ME should decrease as the response increases. Therefore, we calculated the ME from the intercept, specifically at the LLOQ concentration of each compound and calibration model.

Fig. 5. General illustration of the calculation of total ME as a sum of rotational and translational ME. I_M – intercept of the matrix calibration curve, I_{STD} – intercept of the standard calibration curve, $R_{LLOQ,STD}$ – analyte response at the LLOQ levels of the standard calibration curve, ΔI – the difference between the intercepts of the standard and matrix calibration curves, ME_S – matrix effects calculated by comparison of slopes from matrix and standard calibration curves (rotational ME), ME_I – matrix effects calculated by comparison of intercepts from matrix and standard calibration curves (translational ME).

The compounds with ME within $\pm 20\%$, as obtained by the post-extraction addition approach, either exhibited non-significant intercepts, indicating the absence of translational ME, or showed only low translational ME values (<11%) calculated using the proposed equation (1) when the intercept was statistically significant. This confirmed that the slope-based approach provided comparable results to the post-extraction addition approach without the burden of erroneously overestimated results. However, some compounds with post-extraction addition ME higher than 20% also had non-significant intercepts, for example telmisartan and atenolol in the $1/X$ and $1/X^2$ models, and tetracycline in the $1/X^2$ model, confirming the absence of translational ME and a close correlation of ME calculated from slopes and ME obtained by the post-extraction addition approach (Fig. 4 and Table 1).

Unfortunately, the Ln model proved unsuitable for calibration curve intercept-based correction. Although the comparison of intercepts suggested minimal translational ME, substantial discrepancies between slope-based ME and post-extraction ME persisted (SM Fig. S2A), resulting in systematic underestimation.

Fig. 4 shows that the ME from slopes of $1/X^2$ model for tetracycline is close to the ME determined by the post-extraction approach, which was further confirmed by the non-significant intercepts.

A statistically significant intercept was observed predominantly for compounds exhibiting substantial differences between matrix effect obtained by post-extraction addition approach (ME_P) and matrix effect derived from slopes (ME_S). These compounds had significant translational ME, as shown for several compounds, e.g. TTC tetracycline using $1/X$ model, hydrocortisone using $1/X$ and $1/X^2$ models and caffeine for $1/X^0$, $1/X$, and $1/X^2$ models, in Table 1. Therefore, ME derived from intercepts (ME_I) were calculated according to equation (1) for these compounds. Consequently, the sum of ME_S and ME_I was calculated. The detailed numerical ME values obtained for both ionization modes, using the tested approaches, including rotational ME_S , translational ME_I , and reference ME_P at LLOQ, are summarized in Table 3.

For tetracycline ($1/X$ model), a significant intercept resulted in a calculated translational $ME_I \approx 13\%$. and the combined matrix effect ($ME_I + ME_S$) showed substantially improved agreement with reference ME_P (66%) compared to ME_S alone (18%). Even more pronounced

Table 1

Matrix effects of selected compounds calculated by the post-extraction addition approach at LLOQ (ME_P), the slope-based approach (ME_S), and by the proposed equation (4) comparing the intercepts (ME_I) of the standard and matrix calibration models.

	matrix effects [%]											
	$1/X^0$			$1/X$			$1/X^2$			Ln		
	ME_P	ME_S	ME_I	ME_P	ME_S	ME_I	ME_P	ME_S	ME_I	ME_P	ME_S	ME_I
ESI positive												
telmisartan	-	-	-	52	28	n. s.	52	34	n. s.	52	-3	7
atenolol	-	-	-	44	36	n. s.	44	38	n. s.			7
maraviroc	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	45	-4	4
tetracycline	-	-	-	66	18	13	51	25	n. s.	66	-5	13
hydrocortisone	-	-	-	200	0	218	200	0	200	200	-28	41
caffeine	352	3	377	352	5	370	1097	10	1082	352	-38	65
ESI negative												
sofosbuvir	14	-8	13	26	-8	25	26	-7	20	26	-3	4
salicylic acid	122	0	151	122	1	132	122	5	121	122	-18	-21
hydrocortisone	-	-	-	151	0	179	151	8	156	151	-24	54

effects were observed for hydrocortisone and caffeine. In these cases, ME_S values were lower than 10%, whereas large translational ME_I (around 210% and 370%, respectively) were identified, and combined matrix effects ($ME_S + ME_I$) closely corresponded to the reference ME_P at the LLOQ (200% and 352%, respectively). This pattern was consistent across applicable weighting models.

A similar trend was observed in ESI negative. Compounds with reference ME_P within $\pm 20\%$ typically exhibited either insignificant intercepts or only minor translational contributions, and slope-based approach therefore provided comparable results without overestimation. In contrast, for compounds with statistically significant intercepts, namely sofosbuvir, salicylic acid, and hydrocortisone, calibration curve intercept-based calculation revealed a meaningful translational component, and total matrix effect ($ME_S + ME_I$) improved agreement with the reference ME_P . As in ESI positive, the Ln model proved unsuitable for calibration curve intercept-based calculation, as it systematically produced resulting in erroneously underestimated ME than the reference approach.

Overall, these findings demonstrate that integration of slope- and

intercept-based calculations enable more accurate estimation of matrix effects.

3.5. Validation of the newly developed approach

A set of compounds not included in the original set of analytes was used to fully test the suitability and accuracy of the newly developed approach for the calculation of matrix effects based on both intercept and slope. These compounds were measured in three different matrices, i.e., urine, plasma, and apple juice, using generic UHPLC-MS/MS method and sample preparation methods. The obtained data was evaluated using the same protocol as for the original set of compounds. The new approach was used only for compounds for which the intercept was statistically significant with p -value < 0.05 . Fig. 6 shows boxplots summarizing differences between reference ME_P and ME_S calculated by the comparison of slopes and ME calculated by the new approach combining intercept and slope for all three matrices in both ESI positive and negative mode at LLOQ concentrations. The newly developed protocol resulted in calculated ME significantly closer to the true ME_P values with

Fig. 6. Boxplots summarizing the differences between matrix effects calculated by Matuszewski equation (considered 100%), and (1) matrix effects calculated by the comparison of slopes (blue), and (2) matrix effect calculated by the new approach combining intercept and slope (purple). Analytes with statistically significant intercept (SM Table S7) measured in apple juice (A, D), urine (B, E), and plasma (C, F) in positive (A-C) and negative (D-F) ionization mode. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

differences mostly within $\pm 20\%$. On the other hand, the results confirmed that calculation of MEs based only on the slope of calibration curve is unsuitable as the differences were usually around 50% in negative mode and up to thousands of percent in positive mode, especially when measuring plasma and urine samples. All values of calculated ME for all tested compounds with statistically significant intercept are listed in SM Table S7. No significant differences were observed based on the used transformation of the data for calibration curves. This indicates that, independently of the selected data transformation, i.e., $1/X^0$, $1/X$, or $1/X^2$, the new approach is suitable for ME calculation whenever the intercept is statistically significant. However, this approach is not applicable to the Ln calibration model, as discussed in Section 3.4.

The benefits of the new approach are clearly visible, for example on 17α -hydroxyprogesterone measured in plasma. ME_p calculated by Matuszewski equation at LLOQ was +391%, whereas the comparison of slopes resulted in MEs of -31%. Conversely, the new equations (4) and (5) taking into account the slope and intercept led to ME of +374%, closely corresponding to the reference value. Similar trends were observed for other analytes. Riboflavin exhibited ME values of +1791%

when calculated using the Matuszewski equation, +56% using the slope-based approach, and +1916% using the new equations. Likewise, ethyl paraben showed ME values of +3803%, -31%, and +3602%, respectively. All the results discussed so far were focusing on LLOQ concentrations. To fully validate the proposed equations, ME were also calculated at other concentration levels. For this comparison, analytes with significant ME were selected. Fig. 7 shows that the proposed equations can be used to calculate ME at any concentration level with high accuracy as the differences between these calculated ME and the true values were less than 20% for all selected compounds, independently of the dissimilarity of the matrix and standard calibration curve.

The last step of the validation included application of the new approach to data obtained on different instrumentation. All so far discussed validation results were measured on Xevo TQ-XS triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (Waters). Subsequently, we measured selected samples also on 6495 Triple Quadrupole mass spectrometer (Agilent). As shown in Fig. 8, the accuracy of the new approach was independent of the used instrumentation, demonstrating its robustness and broad applicability across different UHPLC-MS/MS platforms. Indeed, different ME were obtained for the same compounds on these two

Fig. 7. Standard (red) and matrix (blue) calibration curves for (A) 17α -hydroxyprogesterone, (B) 11-deoxycortisol, and (C) 5α -dihydrotestosterone measured in plasma and their matrix effect calculated by the new approach combining intercept and slope (pink) and by the reference Matuszewski equation (light blue). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Comparison of matrix effects calculated by comparison of slopes (full color bar), by Matuszewski equation at LLOQ (hatched color bar), and by the new approach combining intercept and slope (color dot) for selected compounds measured in urine: (1) cortisol, (2) androsterone, (3) serotonin, (4) 11-deoxycortisol, (5) isorhamnetin, and (6) ritonavir. $1/X$ weighting was used for data transformation for compounds (1)-(3), $1/X^2$ weighting for compounds (4)-(6). Results from Xevo TQ-XS (A) and Agilent 6495 Triple Quadrupole (B). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

different MS instruments, which is expected given variations in ESI source design and desolvation conditions (e.g., Z-Spray/StepWave ion transfer vs. Jet Stream with superheated sheath gas and iFunnel ion optics). However, the accuracy of the new approach to calculate the ME close to the values obtained by the Matuszewski equation remained unaffected. All results are listed in SM [Table S7](#).

4. Conclusions

In the process of selecting appropriate calibration models based on % error and regression analysis, it was proven that the validity of each model is affected by the defined calibration range. An unweighted linear regression model is not appropriate for wide calibration ranges. The % errors were very high, although it provided the best coefficients of determination. On the other hand, the $1/X^2$ weighting and Ln transformation models were found to be suitable in terms of the acceptable % errors. However, for the $1/X^2$ weighting, a slight visual deviation of the response values from the linear regression was observed for some compounds. Therefore, it was necessary to either exclude the highest concentration points or use quadratic regression. The Ln transformation was the optimal choice with respect to % errors and regression analysis. This model is therefore suggested for linear regression over a wide calibration range.

The post-extraction addition ME evaluation approach confirmed the concentration dependence of ME for most compounds. In general, the slope-based approach showed significantly lower ME compared to the post-extraction addition approach recommended by the EMA guideline and considered as the reference approach. It can be concluded that none of the tested calibration models provided overestimated results compared to the post-extraction addition approach. However, several of them exhibited underestimated results. This can be explained by the fact that translational matrix effects are not included in this evaluation, as they have no effect on the slope. Therefore, it is not advisable to rely on the slope approach as an effective method for obtaining accurate matrix effect results unless a means of calculating translational matrix effects from the intercept is also available.

We propose a new equation (Eq. (4)) that allows the calculation of translational ME based on the comparison of intercepts from standard and matrix calibration curves. The sum of the translational ME from intercepts and rotational ME from the slopes (Eq. (5)) corresponded more closely to the ME determined by the post-extraction addition approach, especially in the case of the $1/X^0$, $1/X$, and $1/X^2$ models. In contrast, the logarithmic transformation still produced significantly underestimated results, i.e., significantly lower ME than the ME obtained by the post-extraction addition approach and compared to the other models. Only very high rotational matrix effects affected the slope of the logarithmic model. Thus, a suitable ME calculation based on the slope and intercept has not yet been found for the Ln model. Compared to other calibration models, the ME obtained by the $1/X^2$ weighting model were in a better agreement with the ME obtained by the post-extraction addition approach, especially at the higher concentration levels. In combination with the translational ME calculated from the intercepts, it enabled the ME to be correctly determined without the need for post-extraction addition experiments. The accuracy of the new approach was tested by analyzing validation set of compounds in three different matrices, i.e., plasma, urine, and apple juice, using two instrumental platforms. The matrix effects calculated by new approach were close to reference values. Therefore, the applicability of the new approach was demonstrated to be independent of the matrix, instrument, and weighting scheme.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Hana Kočová Vlčková: Conceptualization, Data curation, Investigation, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Kateřina Plachká:** Writing – original draft. **František Švec:** Project

administration, Writing – review & editing. **Lucie Nováková:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the project New Technologies for Translational Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences (NETPHARM, CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004607) co-funded by the European Union.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2026.345642>.

Data availability

Data will be made available at Zenodo under the <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20118899>.

References

- [1] R.N. Xu, L. Fan, M.J. Rieser, et al., Recent advances in high-throughput quantitative bioanalysis by LC–MS/MS, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.* 2 (2007) 342–355, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpba.2007.02.006>.
- [2] D.V. Yaroshenko, L.A. Kartsova, Matrix effect and methods for its elimination in bioanalytical methods using chromatography-mass spectrometry, *J. Anal. Chem.* 4 (2014) 311–317, <https://doi.org/10.1134/s1061934814040133>.
- [3] F. Raposo, D. Barceló, Challenges and strategies of matrix effects using chromatography-mass spectrometry: an overview from research versus regulatory viewpoints, *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.* (2021) 116068, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2020.116068>.
- [4] IUPAC, in: *Compendium of Chemical Terminology*, 3.0, 1 ed., International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry, IUPAC, 2019.
- [5] G.G. Guilbault, M. Hjelm, Nomenclature for automated and mechanised analysis (recommendations 1989), *Pure Appl. Chem.* 9 (1989) 1657–1664, <https://doi.org/10.1351/pac198961091657>.
- [6] D. Fernandes Andrade, E.R. Pereira-Filho, D. Amarasiwardena, Current trends in laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy: a tutorial review, *Appl. Spectrosc. Rev.* 2 (2021) 98–114, <https://doi.org/10.1080/05704928.2020.1739063>.
- [7] S.L.R. Ellison, M. Thompson, Standard additions: myth and reality, *Analyst* 8 (2008) 992–997, <https://doi.org/10.1039/B717660K>.
- [8] B.K. Matuszewski, M.L. Constanzer, C.M. Chavez-Eng, Strategies for the assessment of matrix effect in quantitative bioanalytical methods based on HPLC–MS/MS, *Anal. Chem.* 13 (2003) 3019–3030, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac020361s>.
- [9] P. Kebarle, L. Tang, From ions in solution to ions in the gas phase - the mechanism of electrospray mass spectrometry, *Anal. Chem.* 22 (1993) 972A–986A, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac00070a001>.
- [10] P.J. Taylor, Matrix effects: the Achilles heel of quantitative high-performance liquid chromatography–electrospray–tandem mass spectrometry, *Clin. Biochem.* 4 (2005) 328–334, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clinbiochem.2004.11.007>.
- [11] V. Pilařová, K. Plachká, M.A. Khalikova, et al., Recent developments in supercritical fluid chromatography – mass spectrometry: is it a viable option for analysis of complex samples? *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.* (2019) 212–225, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2018.12.023>.
- [12] G.L. Losacco, J.-L. Veuthey, D. Guillaume, Supercritical fluid chromatography – mass spectrometry: recent evolution and current trends, *TrAC, Trends Anal. Chem.* (2019) 731–738, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trac.2019.07.005>.
- [13] N. Fang, S. Yu, M.J.J. Ronis, et al., Matrix effects break the LC behavior rule for analytes in LC-MS/MS analysis of biological samples, *Exp. Biol. Med.* 4 (2014) 488–497, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1535370214554545>.
- [14] P. Panuwet, R.E. Hunter Jr., P.E. D'Souza, et al., Biological Matrix effects in quantitative tandem Mass spectrometry-based analytical methods: advancing biomonitoring, *Crit. Rev. Anal. Chem.* 2 (2016) 93–105, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408347.2014.980775>.
- [15] W.M. Draper, D. Xu, S.K. Perera, Electrolyte-Induced ionization suppression and Microcystin toxins: ammonium formate suppresses sodium replacement ions and enhances protonated and ammoniated ions for improved specificity in quantitative LC-MS-MS, *Anal. Chem.* 10 (2009) 4153–4160, <https://doi.org/10.1021/ac802735t>.

- [16] A. Furey, M. Moriarty, V. Bane, et al., Ion suppression; a critical review on causes, evaluation, prevention and applications, *Talanta* (2013) 104–122, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2013.03.048>.
- [17] A. Cappiello, G. Famigliani, P. Palma, et al., Matrix effects in liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry, *J. Liq. Chromatogr. Relat.* 9–12 (2010) 1067–1081, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10826076.2010.484314>.
- [18] G. Loos, A. Van Schepdael, D. Cabooter, Quantitative mass spectrometry methods for pharmaceutical analysis, *Philos. Trans. A Math. Phys. Eng. Sci.* (2016) 2079, <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2015.0366>.
- [19] A. Nasiri, R. Jahani, S. Mokhtari, et al., Overview, consequences, and strategies for overcoming matrix effects in LC-MS analysis: a critical review, *Analyst* 20 (2021) 6049–6063, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1AN01047F>.
- [20] W. Zhou, S. Yang, P.G. Wang, Matrix effects and application of matrix effect factor, *Bioanalysis* 23 (2017) 1839–1844, <https://doi.org/10.4155/bio-2017-0214>.
- [21] J.E. Adaway, B.G. Keevil, Therapeutic drug monitoring and LC-MS/MS, *J. Chromatogr. B Analyt. Technol. Biomed. Life. Sci.* (2012) 33–49, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2011.09.041>.
- [22] E. Chambers, D.M. Wagrowski-Diehl, Z. Lu, et al., Systematic and comprehensive strategy for reducing matrix effects in LC/MS/MS analyses, *J. Chromatogr. B* 1 (2007) 22–34, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jchromb.2006.12.030>.
- [23] M. Uher, S. Mičuda, M. Kacerovský, et al., An alternative approach to validation of liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry methods for the quantification of endogenous compounds, *J. Chromatogr. A* (2023) 464173, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chroma.2023.464173>.
- [24] J.W. Dolan, Calibration curves, part V: curve weighting, *LC-GC N. Am.* 7 (2009) 534–540.
- [25] W.D. John, Calibration curves III: a different view, *LC-GC N. Am.* 5 (2009) 392–400 [Online]. Available: <https://www.chromatographyonline.com/view/calibration-curves-iii-different-view>.
- [26] W.D. John, Calibration Curves, Part I: to b or not to b? *LC-GC N. Am.* 3 (2009) 224–230 [Online]. Available: <https://www.chromatographyonline.com/view/calibration-curves-part-i-b-or-not-b>.
- [27] [Guideline on Bioanalytical Method Validation, 2011.](#)
- [28] M. Thompson, S.L.R. Ellison, R. Wood, Harmonized guidelines for single-laboratory validation of methods of analysis (IUPAC Technical Report), *Pure Appl. Chem.* 5 (2002) 835–855, <https://doi.org/10.1351/pac200274050835>.
- [29] [Guidelines for the Validation of Chemical Methods for the FDA Foods Program, third ed., 2019, 2019.](#)
- [30] [Safety of the Food Chain Pesticides and Biocides. SANTE/12682/2019. Guidance Document on Analytical Quality Control and Method Validation Procedures for Pesticides Residues Analysis in Food and Feed, 2019.](#)
- [31] H. Truffelli, P. Palma, G. Famigliani, et al., An overview of matrix effects in liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry, *Mass Spectrom. Rev.* 3 (2011) 491–509, <https://doi.org/10.1002/mas.20298>.